

Skewing in Translating English Illocutionary Force into Indonesian

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Abstract: Translation is getting more and more important nowadays, because most of the texts are in foreign language, especially English as an international language which is mostly spoken by the people to communicate all over the world. In the process of translation, translator must discover the meaning of a source language and translate it to the target language which expresses the meaning of the source language in natural way. In translating some sentences types of SL into the TL the translator has the task to discover the meaning (semantic) so that he is able to translate them in natural way, especially in some sentence types which have rhetorical meaning or illocutionary force, which contain other intended meaning. This research is focused on translation in relation to grammatical, semantic structure found in the novels entitled *Family Album* by Steel (1989) and its translation *Album Keluarga* by Prajoko (2005), in order to find out the strategy used by the translators in translating the illocutionary force. Based on the analysis, it was found that the different form of translation used by the translator in order to reach the naturalness of translation in the TL dynamic equivalent. Although there is skewing of form from the source language to the target language, however, semantically, the Indonesian translation carries the same meaning or in other words, it does not change the intended meaning of the SL.

Keywords: Translation, skewing, novel

I. INTRODUCTION

Larson (1998: 3) states that translation is basically a change of form. Translation then consists of studying the lexicon, grammatical structure, communication situation, and cultural context of the source language text, analyzing it in order to determine its meaning, and then reconstructing this same meaning using the lexicon and grammatical structure which are appropriate in the receptor language and its cultural context. He also states that translation consists of transferring the meaning of the source language into the receptor language or the form of the source language is replaced by the form of the receptor language. This is done by going from the form of the first language to the form of a second language by way of semantic structure.

In the process of translation, translator must discover the meaning of a source language and translate it to the target language which expresses the meaning of the source language in natural way. In translating some sentences types of SL into the TL the translator has the task to discover the meaning (semantic) so that he is able to translate them in natural way, especially in some sentence types which have rhetorical meaning or illocutionary force, which contains other intended meaning. After discovering the intended meaning of a sentence, so the translator is able to use the skewing strategy to reconstruct source language to the target language, which may have different sentence type or form but convey the same meaning from the SL into the TL.

Skewing can be from question illocutionary force to command illocutionary force. This example needs to be considered: SL: Peter: "Ladies and Gentlemen, may I have your attention, please?" TL: Peter: "Hadirin yang terhormat, sayamohonperhatiannya." The grammatical meaning of Peter utterance is asking attention from the audience. However, the task of translator, then in translating this example, is to find out something lies behind

the literal or grammatical meaning. In this case the translator have to find the rhetorical meaning or illocutionary force, the illocutionary force in Peter's speech is requesting the audience to be quiet. It is seen that the translator skewed the question illocutionary force to the command illocutionary force from SL to TL.

Levinson (1983: 9), then strengthens this idea, he argues that the task of translator is to find out the meaning or illocutionary force of SL texts and formulate them on the TL by considering the language system and cultural background of the readers.

There are numerous researchers discussed about translation fields, however only one of them discussed about skewing and meaning of the interrogative sentence. Since there are some sentences types which may have rhetorical meaning, and cause problems for translator, so that, by conducting this research I try to analyze the skewing as the strategy for translating English illocutionary force into Indonesian not only in interrogative sentence but some sentences types which occur in the data source.

Referring to the explanation above it is very interesting to find out the strategies for translating illocutionary force based on the skewing in which the translator must consider about the sentence type in which the illocutionary force used. Novel, in this case *Family Album* by Steel (1989) and its translation *Album Keluarga* by Prajoko (2005) serve numerous of illocutionary forces, which needed. So it is very interesting to use those novels as the data source to be analyzed.

1.2 The Problems of the Study

This following discussion is focused on translation in relation to grammatical, semantic structure found in the novels entitled *Family Album* by Steel (1989) and its translation *Album Keluarga* by Prajoko (2005), in order to find out the strategy used by the translators in translating the illocutionary force. This study gives specific emphasis on skewing in terms of illocutionary force and grammatical form proposed by Larson which is then known as skewing of grammatical mood of the sentence and its semantic structure. The strategy used by the translator to translate the speakers' utterances in the novels are based on sentence type in which the sentences or utterances are used, then used the skewing strategies to translate the source language texts to the target language texts, which occur in the novels.

Based on the explanation, there are some problems, will be raised in this study. The problems can be formulated as follows:

1. What kinds of skewing of illocutionary force and grammatical form are found in the source language of the novel *Family Album*?
2. How are the expressions of illocutionary force translated from the source language into the target language?

1.3. The Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study is mainly divided into two: general objective and specific objective. Each of them will be explaining in the following:

1.3.1 General Objectives

This study aimed generally at increasing our perspective on the process of translating illocutionary force into Indonesian based on skewing

1.3.2 Specific Objectives

1. To identify the types of skewing involved in the strategy for translating English illocutionary force into Indonesian
2. To find out how the expressions of English illocutionary force translated from the source language into the target language
3. To find out the equivalent of illocutionary force applied by the translator in translating English illocutionary force into Indonesian

1.4 The Significance of the Study

This study is expected to give positive contribution to the development of translation, as the part of linguistic studies mainly in the field of skewing as strategy for translating English illocutionary force into Indonesian in

Family Album novel by Steel (1989) and its translation *Album Keluarga* novel by Prajoko (2005). Moreover, the result of this study is hoped to assist those who need the reference in conducting the same research.

1.5 The Scope of the Study

The focus of this study is the analysis of the sentence type in relation to the skewing as the strategy for translating the illocutionary force of the source language into the target and the equivalence applied for translating English illocutionary force into Indonesian in *Family Album* novel by Steel (1989) and its translation *Album Keluarga* novel by Prajoko (2005). The discussion of the study will cover:

1. The identification of the types of skewing involved in the strategy for translating English illocutionary force into Indonesian
2. The identification of form of the expressions of English illocutionary force translated from the source language into the target language
3. The identification of equivalent of illocutionary force applied by the translator in translating English illocutionary force into Indonesian.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW, CONCEPTS, AND THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1 Review of Literature

In this sub chapter some review of articles, theses on literature are presented. Some of papers presented in relation to skewing, translation of source language to the target language. Throughout these pieces of works it is hoped that there would be some information that can be of help for the sake of this research.

Loos (2004) in the *Journal of Translation* in the article entitled "Speech Act as an Illocutionary Act" discusses about speech acts in real-life interactions and require not only knowledge of the language but also appropriate use of that language within a given culture. In this article, she analyzes declarative and interrogative sentences which convey secondary meaning.

Pena (2006) in the "The Construction of Away Messages: A Speech Act Analysis" in *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication*, analyzes the categories of speech acts, i.e. assertive, directive, commissive, and expressive

Wardhana (2005) in his thesis entitled *The Illocutionary Force of Sentence Type in The Gospels: A Community Study*, gives contribution in this research. His thesis talks about types of sentences used to express different kinds of illocutionary force by using the theory proposed by some expert in the translation study. The sentences analyzed are declaratives, interrogative, imperatives and exclamatory sentences.

He focuses his analysis on sentence type, which contains the illocutionary force from the source language into the target language, but does not analyze the skewing occurs in the SL to TL this later will differentiate his analysis to the writer's. The difference also lies on the data source from which the data will be taken.

Sugiardi (2006) on *Skewing Analysis on Illocutionary Force In The Translation Of A Play 'Romeo and Juliet'* gives the most contribution in doing my study. On her thesis, she talks a lot about skewing in terms of semantic structure on illocutionary force, mainly illocutionary force and grammatical form by using the theories proposed by some experts in the field of illocutionary force and translation study.

She focuses her analysis on skewing of illocutionary force in the source language to the target language, she does not describe how the sentence type influence the strategy of translating illocutionary force based on skewing, and this later will differentiate her analysis to the writer's. Moreover the difference also lies on the data source from which the data will be taken.

Pratiwi (2009) in her thesis entitled *Skewing And Meaning Of The Interrogative Sentence In The Translation Of "Harry Potter And The Half-Blood Prince By J.K Rowling Into "Harry Potter Dan Pangeran Berdarah Campuran" By Listiana Srisanti*. She analyzes about skewing and meaning of interrogative sentence by using the theory of skewing, illocutionary force and some theories proposed by some experts in the field of translation study. She finds some interrogative sentence which can be used to convey various meanings. They are used to convey: a) statement, b) command, c) anger, d) surprise, e) conviction, f) uncertainty, g) disappointment, h) denial, i) suggestion, j) disagreement, k) confirmation, l) certainty, m) offer

She focuses her analysis on interrogative sentence skewing of illocutionary force in the source language to the target language; this later would differentiate her analysis to the writer's. Moreover the analysis of this study is not only focused in interrogative sentence but also the declarative sentence and imperative sentence, the difference also lies on the data source from which the data was taken.

2.2 Concepts

This study is based on the ideas proposed by some experts in the field of semantic and translation studies. The concepts which have to be considered in this study are: principles translation, skewing, speech act, illocutionary force.

Nida (1975:27) proposes three principles of translation which indicate that no translation in a receptor language can be the exact equivalent of the model in source language. Those strategies are: loss of information, addition of information and skewing of information.

Skewing

Larson (1998:31) states that skewing is the diversity or the lack of one-to-one correlation between form and meaning. The diversity can occur on the level of word to word, phrase to phrase and sentence to sentence. It is also stated that if there were no skewing all lexical items and grammatical forms would have only one meaning. Then, word for word translation would then possible. However, as it is known, any meaning has its own distinctive forms. The semantic structure skewed into different grammatical structure is called skewing.

2.3 Theoretical Framework

This study analyzed based on the theory proposed by some experts in the field of semantic and translation studies. The theories which have to be considered in this study are strategy of translation, speech act, skewing of illocutionary force and grammatical form, and the theory of equivalence.

The Strategy of Translation

Nida (1975:27) explains that all types of translation involve these following conditions, which then in this study those conditions referring to the strategy of translation:

Loss of information

The translation of items in the SL does not explain the whole information in the TL or is not translated or transferred into the TL

Addition of information

The translation of items in the source language into target language is with addition of extra information.

Skewing of information

The translation of items from the source language is not the exact equivalence in the target language.

III. METHOD OF RESEARCH

This chapter describes the research method used in writing this thesis. The explanation includes data source, method and technique of data collection, and finally method and technique of presenting of data analysis. The method applied in this study is library research, which refers to the findings and collecting some information from various kinds of references that have close relation to this study. The detail is presented in the further discussion.

3.1 Data Source

In defining the data source of this study, novel entitled *Family Album* novel by Steel (1989) and its translation *Album Keluarga* novel by Prajoko (2005) were chosen as the data to be analyzed.

This novel and its translation were chosen as the data source, because they provide the data, which considered being relevant with the problems raised and analyzed in this thesis. The story of this novel represents a real life

of a family, so that the English used in this novel also represents the English used in real life, and it is written by the author of best selling novel. Besides, the writer can also find the skewing as the strategy for translating the English source text into the Target language text.

3.2 Method and Technique of Data Collection

Sudaryanto (1993: 136-137) proposes that in collecting the data of linguistic studies, generally, there are two methods that can be concerned, they are attentive observation and interview. Attentive observation is the method of collecting the data which is done through the attentive observation of the language use. Meanwhile interview is a method which is done through the conversation (directly) between the observer and the informant or resource person. Since the data taken from written material based on printed-out texts, so the attentive observation was chosen as the method of collecting the data.

In the process of observing, firstly observation was directly done to discover the sentence type of the utterances, which contains illocutionary force in the SLT and its translation in the TLT. After determining the sentences type, the writer identified the skewing as the strategy in translating the illocutionary force of the sentence types, then found their equivalent in the TL.

The samples of texts, which were predicted as illocutionary forces, were selected based on the concept which proposed. Those texts, which consist of illocutionary forces, were chosen for the sake of the aim of the research. The illocutionary forces were analyzed based on the theory which proposed. In the process of taking data, the sentences showing the occurrence of skewing presented for the purpose of obtaining the evidence of the skewing process.

3.3 Method and Technique of Analyzing Data

The method and technique of analyzing data is conducted by using qualitative method as proposed by Sudaryanto (1993). Qualitative method is the method in which it is not designed the statistic procedure in analyzing the data. The phenomenology perspective is used in qualitative method. Since the data is in form of word or sentences, so the qualitative observation is descriptive.

The data which have been collected will be classified into classification of problems. Both data of SL and TL are put one after another to make it easier to conduct the analysis.

The Analysis of the texts will be presented into different sub-discussion. First, the data will be grammatically analyzed to get the idea of how they are constructed, and to see the type of sentence of the source language and in the target language. Analyzing the illocutionary force and their equivalent in TL based on the theory, which proposed. Analyzing the strategy used by the translator in translating the illocutionary forces based on skewing.

IV. SKEWING IN TRANSLATING ENGLISH ILLOCUTIONARY FORCE INTO INDONESIAN IN “FAMILY ALBUM” AND “ALBUM KELUARGA”

The data are presented both in the source language and the target language. The translation of the source language into the target language was analyzed based on skewing. The discussion involves skewing of declarative sentences. After observing and classifying the data, the declarative sentences can be used to convey various meaning namely declarative sentence can convey support, advice, invitation, suggestion, command, pride, permission, distrust, certainty and offer.

4.1 Declarative Sentence

The data shows that the declarative sentence can be used to convey various meanings and in translating those declarative sentences which have secondary meanings, the translator tends to skewed the SL into different form of TL or keep the form of SL in the TL. There are declarative used to convey: (1) support, (2) advice (3) invitation, (4) suggestion, (5) command, (6) pride, (7) permission, (8) distrust and (9) certainty (10) Offer. The analyses are presented in this following discussion.

4.1.1 Declarative Sentence Conveying Support

The following expression is the example of declarative sentence which conveys support. The declarative sentence has straightforward relation to 'statement' however, semantically, the SL has secondary function that is conveying support and it is skewed to 'command' illocutionary force, which is grammatically in form of imperative sentence in the TL which semantically has same secondary function. The example can be seen as in below:

Example (1):

The source language text (p. 20)

Faye: Yes, it is. *In a place like this, that's a lot to be grateful for. Look around you everyday...look at the boys wounded and crippled and maimed... the one's who're never going home at all...*

The target language text (p.33)

Faye: " *Tentusajacukup*". *Di _____ tempatsepertini, kitaharusbersyukurkarenamasihhidup. Lihatlahkesekililingmusetiaphari, lihatlah orang-orang yang terluka, cacat, ataubuntung, orang-orang yang tidakmungkinbisapulaglgi.*"

From the text above it is clearly recognized that grammatically the SL is in form of declarative sentence. This declarative sentence is not used to state something it conveys secondary function that is support to the listener. Looking at the context which involves Faye and ward in a private conversation, in that moment Faye came to Guadalcanal (the place of the American soldier), she came to this place to support the soldiers in the terrible war by conducting a concert, and she met Ward there. Ward was one of American soldier who tried to survive in the war, however he was so hopeless and he remembered about his wife's death in the war, then he shared his life story to Faye. Faye tried to support him, when he felt so hopeless and she reminded that he must thank to God that he was still alive and still in good condition not like his other friends who wounded or even died in the war. Faye tried to make Ward tough and survive in that terrible condition. Semantically, the declarative sentence conveys support to Ward when he is hopeless due to his physical and physiological suffering in the terrible war. Based on the concept of skewing proposed by Larson, the declarative sentence above carries secondary function that is conveying support, so there is skewing between grammatical form and semantic structure occurs in the SLT.

The strategy used by the translator to translate the SL illocutionary force is the strategy of skewing from the SL illocutionary force which is grammatically in form of declarative sentence which has straightforward relation to 'statement' which semantically has secondary function that is conveying support and it is skewed to 'command' illocutionary force, which is grammatically in form of imperative clause in the TL which semantically has same secondary function that is conveying support to the addressee.

The Indonesian translation of the sentence above shows skewing (a declarative sentence into imperative sentence). It can be seen that the translator used the different form to translate the SL declarative sentence into TL imperative sentence. At first, the translator is able to understand the context then translate the source language to the target language in natural way.

In translating the English illocutionary force into Indonesian, the translator tries to reach the naturalness of expression, thus it could be seen that the translator tries to reach the dynamic equivalence. Although there is skewing from the source language to the target language (declarative sentence to imperative sentence) However, semantically, the Indonesian translation carries the same meaning.

4.1.2 Declarative Sentence Conveying Advice

Declarative sentence which conveys advice found in the novel. The declarative sentence has straightforward relation to 'statement' however, semantically, the SL has secondary function that is conveying advice and the translator skewed the declarative sentence to 'command' illocutionary force, which is grammatically in form of imperative sentence in the TL which semantically has same meaning. The example can be seen as in below:

Example (2):

The source language text (p.20)

Faye : "That is terrible thing to say"

The target language text (p.33)

Faye : "Janganberkatasepertiitu"

Syntactically, the SL is in form of declarative sentence. This declarative sentence is not used to state something; however it conveys secondary function that is to give advice to the listener. In that moment, Faye involved in a private conversation with Ward who shared his life story to her, he felt so hopeless because of his death wife. He told Faye that he would not care of himself anymore, whether he lived or died, he thought nobody would care. Then Faye tried to give advice to him by saying "that is terrible thing to say", so, from this expression it can be seen that, semantically, the declarative sentence conveys advice to Ward when he was hopeless due to his physical and physiological suffering in the terrible war.

The SL illocutionary force which is grammatically in form of declarative sentence which has straightforward relation to 'statement', which semantically has secondary function that is conveying advice and it is skewed to 'command' illocutionary force, which is grammatically in form of imperative clause in the TL which semantically has same secondary function that is conveying advice to the addressee. So, it can be recognized that there is skewing between grammatical form and semantic structure occurs in the SL.

Based on the concept of skewing proposed by Larson, the translator applies the skewing as the strategy in translating the SL illocutionary force into the TL that is skewing from declarative sentence into imperative.

The translator used the different form to translate the SL declarative sentence into TL imperative sentence. At first, the translator is able to understand the context then translate the source language to the target language in natural way.

In translating the English illocutionary force into Indonesian, the translator tries to reach the naturalness of expression; translator tries to reach the dynamic equivalence. Although there is skewing from the source language to the target language (declarative sentence to imperative sentence) However, semantically, the Indonesian translation carries the same meaning.

4.1.3 Declarative Sentence Conveying Invitation

The example of declarative sentence which conveys invitation is found in the data. The declarative sentence has straightforward relation to 'statement' however, semantically; the SL has secondary function that is conveying invitation and in translating the SL illocutionary force into the TL, the translator keeps the SL form. The example can be seen as in below:

Example (3):

The source language text (p.23)

Ward: "Maybe we can catch a quick cup of coffee tomorrow morning."

The target language text (p. 38)

Ward: "Mungkinitasempatminum kopi sebentar."

The occurrence of the skewing in terms of the meaning of the illocutionary force can be discovered from the example 4 above. The SL expression is in form of declarative sentence. This declarative expression shows secondary function or illocutionary force that is to invite the listener.

In that moment, Faye involved in a private conversation with Ward. Both of them were in love; however the place where they met was very terrible, the place was in the camp of the American soldier who tried to survive from the World War I. The next day Faye had finished her charity concert there (Guadalcanal, the place of American soldier) and before she would like to leave that place, Ward tried to invite her to get a cup of coffee, by saying 'maybe we can catch a quick a cup of coffee tomorrow morning.' This expression is uttered by Ward who would like to meet her again the next day by inviting her to get a cup of coffee before she left that place.

So, from this expression it is found that, semantically, the declarative sentence conveys invitation to the addressee, Faye. So, it can be recognized that there is skewing between grammatical form and semantic structure occurs in the SL.

The SL illocutionary force which is grammatically in form of declarative sentence which has straightforward relation to 'statement', which semantically has secondary function that is conveying invitation and in translating this expression the translator keeps the SL form in the TL which semantically has same secondary function that is conveying invitation to the addressee. The translator used the same form to translate the SL declarative sentence into TL. At first, the translator is able to understand the context then translate the source language to the target language by trying to keep the SL form into the TL; so that it is found that the translator tries to reach the grammatical equivalence in translating the SL to TL. Although there is skewing between grammatical form and semantic structure occurs in the SL, however the translator is able to keep the SL form in the TL.

4.1.4 Declarative Sentence Conveying Suggestion

The example of declarative sentence which conveys suggestion is found in the data. The declarative sentence has straightforward relation to 'statement' however, semantically; the SL has secondary function that is conveying suggestion and in translating the SL illocutionary force into the TL, the translator keeps the SL form. The example can be seen as in below:

Example (4):

The source language text (p. 49)

Ward: "I think we'd better go. I made reservation at nine."

The target language text (p. 74)

Ward: "Sebaiknyakitaberangkatsekarang. Akusudahmemesantempatuntuk jam Sembilan."

To start the analysis on the illocutionary force of the SL and the TL above certainly the occurrence of the skewing in terms of the meaning of the illocutionary force can be discovered. Syntactically, such the expression which is underlined in the example 5 above is a 'declarative' sentence. As it is stated in Larson's chart of grammatical form and its illocutionary force, the 'declarative' grammatical form typically has illocutionary force of a 'statement'. This is the illocutionary force which is directed through the direct relation between grammatical form and its illocutionary force. The SL which is in form of declarative sentence is not used to state something; however it conveys secondary function that is to suggest the listener.

In that moment, Ward had an appointment with Faye for dinner, and then he came to Faye's house to fetch her. When he arrived at her house, she invited him to see her library and offered a drink. When Faye offered the second drink he declined it then suggesting her to go for dinner because he had made a reservation at nine, Since the time approached the time of the dinner so he suggested her to go by saying 'I think we'd better go'. It is found that semantically, the declarative sentence conveys suggestion to Faye to go for dinner. So, it can be recognized that there is skewing between grammatical form and semantic structure occurs in the SL.

The SL illocutionary force which is grammatically in form of declarative sentence has straightforward relation to 'statement' which semantically has secondary function that is conveying suggestion. In translating this expression the translator keeps the SL form in the TL which semantically has same secondary function that is conveying suggestion to the addressee.

The translator used the same form to translate the SL declarative sentence into TL. At first, the translator is able to understand the context then translate the source language to the target language by trying to keep the SL form into the TL; so that it is found that the translator tries to reach the grammatical equivalence in translating the SL to TL. Although there is skewing between grammatical form and semantic structure occurs in the SL, however the translator is able to keep the SL form in the TL which semantically, the TL (Indonesian translation) carries the same meaning.

4.1.5 Declarative Sentence Conveying command

The following expression is the example of declarative sentence which conveys invitation. The declarative sentence has straightforward relation to 'statement' however, semantically; the SL has secondary function that is conveying invitation and in translating the SL illocutionary force into the TL, the translator skewed the SL 'declarative' form into 'imperative' in the TL form. The illustration of how such declarative sentence can be used to state command will be discussed as follows:

Example (5):

The source language text (p.71)

Faye: "I want you to stop that, Ward"

The target language text (p. 105)

Faye: "Janganteruskanlagi, Ward"

The example 7 above shows the presence of skewing in terms of the meaning of the illocutionary force. From the grammar side, the expression 'I want you to stop that Ward' is a declarative sentence. This declarative grammatical form has direct relation to the 'illocutionary force' of statement however the intention of the speaker uttering this utterance is not to state something; the speaker actually means more than to state something. Then, it is seen that this expression conveys secondary function that is to give command to the listener.

In that moment, Ward told his feeling to Faye that he would like to walk on a serious relationship with her. However she did not believe Ward because she knew that Ward was a playboy millionaire like what she read on the newspaper. Ward kept trying to make her trust his serious intention, by planning to get married to her soon if she would like to resign to be an actress. He kept trying to persuade Faye to resign from the entertainment world then got married to him soon after she had finished her contract of her last film. Faye still did not trust him and did not want to resign to be an actress because she was at the peak of her career, so by saying 'I want you to stop that Ward' actually means giving a command to Ward to stop persuading her. Thus it is seen that semantically, the declarative sentence conveys command to Ward. So this expression shows skewing between grammatical form and semantic structure occurs in the SL

The SL illocutionary force which is grammatically in form of declarative sentence which has straightforward relation to 'statement' which semantically has secondary function that is conveying command is skewed to 'command' illocutionary force, which is grammatically in form of imperative clause in the TL, which semantically has same secondary function that is conveying command to the addressee. It is recognized although there is skewing from the source language to the target language (declarative sentence to imperative sentence) However, semantically, the Indonesian translation carries the same meaning. The translator used the different form to translate the SL declarative sentence into TL imperative sentence. From the example which is presented in the example 7 above, the translator is able to understand the context then translate the source language to the target language in natural way. In addition the skewing as the strategy of translating English illocutionary force into Indonesian is applied by the translator; it is done because the translator tries to reach the naturalness of expression in other words the translator tries to reach the dynamic equivalence.

4.1.6 Declarative Sentence Conveying Pride

The example of declarative sentence conveying pride is also found in the data source. In this following example, the translator applies the skewing as the strategy in translating the SL illocutionary force into the TL that is skewing from 'declarative' sentence into 'interrogative'. The analysis of declarative sentence conveying proud which translated into interrogative sentence is presented as follows:

Example (6):

The source language text (p.167)

Faye: "He looks so sweet"

The target language text (p. 234)

Faye: "Iamanis, bukan?"

Deriving the analysis through the example 8 above, it is clearly realized that the SL declarative sentence conveys secondary meaning in other words there is skewing in terms of the illocutionary force. The expression 'He looks so sweet' which is uttered by the speaker actually means more than to state something; it conveys pride.

In that given situation, Faye and her family attended the graduation of their oldest son named Lionel. Her mind was entirely concentrated on her oldest son, standing so beautiful and innocent and tall, singing the school song, his diploma in his hand, as the sunlight streamed into the room. Then Faye looked at her son, knowing that that moment would never come again. She thought that he would never be this young, or this pure. Life was just beginning for him and she wished so many things for him as the tears poured down her cheeks. Then she turned and looked at her son with a feeling of proud by saying and whispering to her husband 'He looks so sweet', from this expression it can be seen that, semantically, the declarative sentence conveys pride.

Grammatically, the SL illocutionary force has a grammatical form which has straightforward relation to 'statement' which semantically has secondary function that is conveying pride and the translator skew to 'question' illocutionary force, which corresponds directly to interrogative grammatical form in the TL which semantically has same secondary function that is conveying the feeling of pride of the oldest son. So, it can be recognized that there is skewing between grammatical form and semantic structure occurs in the SL.

The skewing in the grammatical form is available since the grammatical form in the SL is not equivalent with the one in the TL. The skewing occurs from the declarative grammatical form in the SL to the interrogative grammatical form in the TL. It is seen in translating the English illocutionary force into Indonesian, the translator tries to reach the naturalness of expression; translator tries to reach the dynamic equivalence. Although there is skewing from the source language to the target language (declarative sentence to interrogative sentence) However, semantically, the Indonesian translation carries the same meaning. In translating the illocutionary force, firstly, the translator is able to understand the context then translate the source language to the target language in natural way. .

4.1.7 Declarative Sentence Conveying Permission

The declarative sentence can also be used to convey permission. The declarative sentence has straightforward relation to 'statement' however, semantically, the SL has secondary function that is conveying permission and the strategy used by the translator in translating this such declarative sentence can be seen that translator change the form of the 'declarative' into 'imperative' grammatical form. The analysis and example of this 'declarative' sentence can be seen as in below:

Example (7):

The source language text (p. 171)

Ward: "It doesn't matter what he wears"

The target language text (p.238)

Ward: "Janganreweltentangbajunya."

The given data which underlined above shows that there is the presence of skewing in terms of meaning occurs in the SL. As it is seen, grammatically, the SL has 'declarative' grammatical form. The 'declarative' has direct relation to 'statement' illocutionary force, however, having seen to the context, the 'declarative' grammatical form is not used to state something, there is an intended meaning which is conveyed by the speaker or in other word it is used rhetorically by the speaker, Ward would like to give permission to George (his son) to wear the wrinkled tees shirt and jeans. Deriving from this explanation it can be seen that, semantically, the 'declarative' sentence conveys secondary meaning that is conveying permission.

In the context, after the graduation of the oldest son (Lionel) of Ward and Faye, they made a party for their son. In that party Lionel invited his friends to his house. That night, there were hundred people. Ward and Faye had arranged for a rock band to play under a tent in the backyard. It was the biggest party they had given in years, and the whole family got excited about it. In the party Greg, their second son, was wearing a wrinkled tee shirt and jeans. Faye was about to send him back up stair but he escaped, and when she said something to Ward he said like what he always did, 'Let him have a good time tonight. It doesn't matter what he wears'. The speaker,

Ward is not simply state or inform something, however this expression conveys secondary meaning that is conveying permission thus it is recognized that there is skewing of illocutionary force occurs in the SL.

Concerning to the TL translation, the translator uses different form to translate the SL illocutionary force to the TL. As it is analyzed, the TL has 'imperative' grammatical form. Considering the concept of skewing proposed by Larson, being 'imperative' grammatical form has direct corresponds to 'command' illocutionary force. In the TL the 'imperative' indicates the direct command used by Ward, which conveys the same intended meaning with the SL conveying permission.

Deriving from the explanation, the translator applies the skewing as the strategy in translating the SL illocutionary force into the TL that is skewing in terms of grammatical form that is from 'declarative' sentence into 'imperative'. In translating the English illocutionary force into Indonesian, the translator tries to reach the naturalness of expression; translator tries to reach the dynamic equivalence. It is found the translator is able to understand the context then translate the source language to the target language in natural way. The SL and TL have the same meaning or illocutionary force, which is conveying that is conveying permission.

4.1.8 Declarative Sentence Conveying Distrust

The data also shows the use of declarative sentence conveying distrust. In this following example, the translator applies the skewing as the strategy in translating the SL illocutionary force into the TL that is skewing from 'declarative' sentence into 'interrogative'. The analysis of 'declarative' sentence conveying distrust which translated into 'interrogative' sentence is presented as follows:

Example (8):

The source language text (p. 404)

Valerie Thayer: "You're out of your mind"

The target language text (p.554)

Valerie Thayer: "kausudahgila, ya?"

The text of SL and TL in the example 10 above obviously indicates the existence of skewing of illocutionary force. Generally the expression like 'you're out of your mind' in the SL is a 'declarative' sentence. This 'declarative' sentence or 'declarative' grammatical form takes the 'statement' as it is illocutionary force. Being a 'statement', the speaker actually wants to state something. The utterance in the SL is not aimed at making 'a statement' or to give information about something, however, it conveys secondary function which semantically, it conveys the distrust to the addressee. So that, it is found that there is presence of skewing of illocutionary force in the SL.

The utterance in the context which spoken by Valerie conveys distrust. Valerie was a new actress; she started her career only as an actress figure, which was actually not an important character, whereas her mother was a great actress and a great film director. However her relationship with her mother was not good, she was not a good daughter, she always made her mother disappointed. One day her mother called her agent and asked Valerie to read for her new film. Then Valerie's agent called her to follow her mother's casting, thus Valerie did not trust her agent by saying 'you're out of your mind'. The speaker, Valerie was not simply state or inform something, however this expression conveys secondary meaning that is conveying distrust thus it is found that the presence of skewing of illocutionary force occurs in the SL.

From grammar point of view, such sentence 'you're out of your mind' takes the form of 'declarative' sentence. This form correlates to the illocutionary force of 'statement' which semantically has secondary function that is conveying distrust and it is skewed to 'interrogative' sentence which correlates to 'question' illocutionary force the TL which semantically has same secondary function that is conveying distrust to the addressee. So, the expression above clearly indicates the occurrence of skewing between grammatical form and semantic structure occurs in the data.

In the TL translation, the translator uses different form to translate the SL illocutionary force to the TL. As it is analyzed, in the expression 'kausudahgila, ya?' indicates the use of 'interrogative' grammatical form. Considering the concept of skewing proposed by Larson, being 'interrogative' grammatical form has direct corresponds to 'question' illocutionary force. In the TL the 'interrogative' which conveys the same intended meaning with the SL conveying distrust.

The expression shows that the translator applies the skewing of grammatical form as the strategy in translating the SL illocutionary force into the TL that is skewing from 'declarative' sentence into 'interrogative'. The translator used the different form to translate the SL 'declarative' sentence into TL 'interrogative' sentence. Although there is skewing from the source language to the target language (declarative sentence to interrogative sentence) However, semantically, the Indonesian translation carries the same meaning. In addition it is found before translating the SL, the translator is able to understand the context then translate the source language to the target language in natural way.

4.1.9 Declarative Sentence Conveying Certainty

The example of 'declarative' sentence conveying certainty is also found in the data source. In this following example, the translator applies the skewing as the strategy in translating the SL illocutionary force into the TL that is skewing from 'declarative' sentence into 'interrogative', in which it has the same meaning in the TL. The analysis of 'declarative' sentence conveying certainty which translated into 'interrogative' sentence is presented as follows:

Example (9):

The source language (p. 422)

George: "It is true!"

The target language text (p. 578)

George: "Memangbegitukenyataannya, kan?"

Having compared the SL to the TL above, it is obviously recognized that there is skewing in terms of the illocutionary force. The expression in the SL indicates the declarative sentence. This declarative sentence is used more than to state something and it conveys secondary function that is conveying certainty to the listener. The utterance 'it is true' in the SL is not aimed at giving give information about something or state about something, however, it conveys secondary function which semantically, it conveys the certainty to the addressee. Therefore, the existence of skewing of illocutionary force is clearly seen in the SL.

In the given context, George was in a private conversation with Valerie. They talked about Valerie's apartment which was actually in a bad condition and environment. The apartment was located in a prostitution area. George was really mad having seen the situation where his girlfriend stayed, he gave a critique to his girlfriend about that apartment and Valerie said to him that his comment about that apartment was a wicked critique, however George was really sure about his judgment by saying 'it's true'. So, from this expression it can be seen that, semantically, the declarative sentence conveys certainty of his judgment about Valerie's apartment.

Grammatically, the SL illocutionary force which conveys certainty has declarative form. The declarative sentence correlates to 'statement'. In translating this expression, the translator skews to 'question' illocutionary force, which correlates to interrogative form. So, it can be recognized that there is skewing between grammatical form and semantic structure occurs in the in the above data.

It is seen that the translator applies the skewing as the strategy in translating the SL illocutionary force into the TL that is skewing from declarative sentence into interrogative. The translator used the different form to translate the SL declarative sentence into TL interrogative sentence. However, this way of translating does not convey the same message since in the TL the expression does not reflect the certainty. So that, it is found that the translator is not able to reach the dynamic or grammatical equivalent in translating the above expression.

4.1.10 Declarative Sentence Conveying Offer

The example of declarative sentence conveying offering is also found in the data source. In this following example, the translator keeps the form of the SL illocutionary force in the TL in translating in which it has the same meaning in the TL. The analysis of declarative sentence conveying offering which translated into is presented as follows:

Example (10)

The source language text (p. 16)

Ward: "I think I can dig something up for you somewhere else."

The target language text (p. 29)

Ward: "Aku rasa akubisamencarikanmakanan di tempat lain."

To focus the attention to the above expression, it is found that there is skewing of illocutionary force. As it is declarative sentence, it generally has the illocutionary force of 'statement', however, the SL declarative sentence of above expression is not used to give information about something or to state something; it conveys secondary function that is to offer someone to do something by saying 'I think I can dig something up for you somewhere else'. Therefore, the skewing of illocutionary force is clearly seen in the SL.

What the speaker intends to achieve by saying the expression is not simply to gain of some information. Actually the speaker's intention is more than to state something. In that given context, Ward was with Faye tried to find something to eat in the camp. They were starving at that time, especially Faye who had performed for hours and had been touring the base, shaking hands, for three hours. Then Ward offered to get something to eat for her by saying 'I think I can dig something up for you somewhere else'. From this expression it is recognized that, semantically, the declarative sentence conveys offer to Faye when she starved, then Ward offer to get something to eat for her.

Following what Larson says the 'declarative' SL illocutionary force has one-to-one correspondence with the illocutionary force of 'statement' however, in the above text the SL, semantically, has secondary function that is conveying offer to the addressee. In translating the SL illocutionary force, the existence of grammatical equivalent is found, since the translator tries to keep the SL form in the TL. The SL illocutionary force which is grammatically in form of declarative sentence has straightforward relation to 'statement' which semantically has secondary function that is conveying offer is translated into 'declarative' form in the TL which conveys the same meaning. So, it is recognized in translating this expression the translator keeps the SL form in the TL which semantically has same secondary function that is conveying offer.

To be able to translate the SL illocutionary force which in the TL conveys the same meaning, firstly, the translator is able to understand the context then translate the source language to the target language. Although there is skewing of illocutionary force occurs in the SL, however the translator is able to keep the SL form in the TL which semantically, the TL (Indonesian translation) carries the same meaning.

V. CONCLUSION

5.1 Conclusion

This study presents about the strategy in translating English illocutionary force into Indonesian in "Family Album" by Steel (1989) and its translation Album Keluarga by Prajoko (2005). Their translation and equivalent is also concerned here. Based on the foregoing analysis and discussion, there are some conclusion that can be drawn.

Firstly, semantically, some expressions in the novel entitled "Family Album" by Steel (1989) convey secondary meaning or illocutionary force, thus there are skewing in terms of grammatical form and semantic structure, since there is diversity between form and meaning. Those expressions are: declarative and interrogative sentences. In translating those expressions, the translator tends to translate them in two ways namely: the translator tends to skew those forms of sentences from SL into TL or keep the SL form into the TL.

5.2 Suggestion

In analyzing translation such phenomenon which frequently occurs in the process of translation and in the translation product like skewing of illocutionary force as well as skewing of the grammatical form needs considering. Besides, the equivalence that has an important role in reaching the naturalness in translation must also be concerned because in reaching the naturalness of the translation the translator must discover the intended meaning or rhetorical meaning of every expression, thus the translator is able to use the skewing of grammatical

form to translate them. These characteristics of the translation are essential for finding out the meaning of the text.

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